

A minimal dispersion flow algorithm

John B. Lindsay

Geography, Environment and Geomatics
University of Guelph
Guelph, Canada
jlindsay@uoguelph.ca

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Abstract—Over the past four decades numerous dispersive (multiple flow direction) flow algorithms have been proposed. Dispersive algorithms are often preferred for applications because they overcome the limitations of the main non-dispersive method, D8, specifically the unnatural appearing extensive straight/parallel flow patterns and the abundance of artifact source cells (ASCs). An ASC is a cell in a flow-direction (FD) raster that has no inflowing cells but is not situated at a summit within the digital elevation model. They represent locations where a flow line has been truncated in the upslope direction, disconnecting the flow line from its starting peak. Attempts to address the unnatural flow patterns of D8 using alternate non-dispersive flow algorithms have resulted in more abundant ASCs. Dispersive flow algorithms can yield more natural appearing flow patterns than D8 while reducing or eliminating ASCs. However, some researchers have argued that dispersion has little physical basis in the definition of upslope area and should be minimized in the formulation of these methods. It seems that a fundamental compromise in flow-path modelling exists between natural-looking flow patterns, the abundance of ASCs, and the need for dispersion. A new minimal dispersion flow algorithm (MDFA) is presented in this paper. MDFA restricts dispersion to locations where it is necessary to resolve ASCs in a non-dispersive path-corrected FD raster. A case study is presented, comparing flow algorithms for the prevalence of ASCs and the amount of dispersion in various non-dispersive and dispersive methods. Findings show that MDFA can produce the natural appearing flow patterns of a path-corrected non-dispersive flow algorithm, eliminates ASCs entirely, while requiring the least number of cells with multiple outflowing neighbors and the lowest average overall dispersion of any of the tested dispersive methods.

I. INTRODUCTION

A flow line traces the route that a theoretical rain drop takes from a peak, downslope to the catchment outlet. If we assume that overland flow is controlled solely by gravity, flow lines follow paths of steepest descent, or slope lines, that are perpendicular to

contour lines along their entire length [1]. Every point on the topographic surface belongs to one flow line, connecting that location to an upslope peak (summit) and a downslope outlet. Because there are infinite points on a surface, there are also infinite flow lines. Flow lines converge downslope in channels and upslope at ridges. The downslope direction of the flow line at a point is called the flow direction (FD) and is equivalent to aspect. Flow algorithms are used to derive FD rasters, which specify the upslope-downslope connections among grid cells and their neighbors, allowing for individual (approximated) flow lines, or flow paths, to be traced.

A source cell is a grid cell in an FD raster that has no inflowing neighbor. These cells are the starting points of flow lines. An artifact source cell (ASC) is a grid cell that has one or more higher neighbors in the digital elevation model (DEM), none of which flow into the cell in the FD raster. They are therefore non-summit flow line starting points. ASCs are somewhat analogous to artifact depressions, artificially truncating the path of a flow line, but in an upslope rather than downslope direction. They disconnect flow lines from their true starting points at summits. ASCs occur because FD rasters are necessarily finite representations of the infinite field of flow lines and because many flow algorithms crudely approximate flow directions, i.e., aspect.

FD rasters created using non-dispersive algorithms (single flow direction algorithms), such as D8 [2], possess more ASCs than those created using dispersive flow algorithms. D8 is the oldest, simplest, and most commonly applied method for routing surface flows based on DEMs. However, this algorithm is known to suffer many limitations, most notably it produces unnatural-appearing parallel flow patterns. This occurs because of the combination of crudely representing FD in intervals of 45° (8 directions), which causes a directional bias, and because of the algorithm's inability to represent flow divergence. While many researchers have discussed D8's unnatural flow patterns, far fewer

have acknowledged the abundance of ASCs in D8 FD rasters as an issue [3]. ASCs are distributed throughout D8 FD rasters but are particularly common along ridges. That is, D8's approximated flow lines start at drainage divides, and do not continue along the divide upwards toward the summit. Because flow lines converge upslope at divides (note, upslope convergence is equivalent to downslope divergence, which non-dispersive algorithms do not allow), D8 cannot represent flow divergence along ridges.

Several other non-dispersive algorithms have been developed to overcome the unnatural-looking flow patterns produced by D8. Fairfield and Leymarie [4] developed the Rho8 flow algorithm which reduces D8's directional bias, but suffers from the fact that it is stochastic, and thus produces a different result each time it is run on a data set. Gallant and Wilson [3] also recognized that Rho8 produces many times more ASCs than D8. Orlandini [5] proposed two non-dispersive flow algorithms, D8-LAD/LTD, that make path-based adjustments to individual FDs to better align with the overall path of flow lines, substantially reducing the directional bias of D8. However, this approach also produces abundant ASCs.

Why do attempts to correct D8's directional bias result in greater prevalence of ASCs? ASC are potentially introduced in flow pattern when an FD is deflected away from its D8 direction to a neighboring cell to better align with the flow-line aspect. The deflection causes the abandoned cell to be cut off from its upslope flow line. Unless another deflection redirects a neighboring parallel flow line toward the abandoned cell, it will become an ASC. Because these methods purposely reduce the occurrence of parallel flow patterns, this rectifying condition is unlikely to occur, and ASCs become abundant. This is an inherent property of nondispersive methods that break up parallel flow patterns and represents part of a *fundamental compromise of flow-path modelling*. We must either accept parallel non-dispersive flow patterns with fewer artifact source cells (D8), more-natural non-dispersive flow patterns with abundant artifact source cells (Rho8, D8-LAD/LTD), or dispersive flow.

Like the presence of parallel flow patterns, dispersion has the effect of reducing the occurrence of ASCs in FD rasters. In fact, not all flow algorithms produce ASCs. Fully dispersive flow algorithms that distribute flow to all downslope neighbors, such as Freeman's multiple-direction D8 (MD8) algorithm [6], and its many variants [7,8], do not create ASCs. However, these methods tend to be overly dispersive [9]. For example, with MD8, flow issuing from a point near the top of a conical surface will eventually flow to the opposite side of the cone. Increasing MD8's dispersion-dampening parameter cannot rectify this issue. Tarboton [10] argues that dispersion is inconsistent with the physical definition of upslope area, and that dispersion should be minimized to the extent possible in development of flow algorithms. If necessary, he states, physical dispersion can be modeled separately. Tarboton's D_∞ method is an example of a dispersion-limiting flow algorithm, where flow is restricted to at most two adjacent downslope cells.

In this paper we describe a new flow algorithm that creates flow patterns with no ASCs and with minimal flow dispersion, by restricting dispersion to cells where it is necessary to resolve the ASCs in a non-dispersive FD raster.

II. MINIMAL DISPERSION FLOW ALGORITHM (MDFA)

The new minimal dispersion flow algorithm (MDFA) is conceptually simple. It begins by deriving a D8 FD raster from a depressionless DEM. Then, each flow path in this grid is traversed in the downslope direction, from longest to shortest, applying a path-based directional bias correction, somewhat similar to Orlandini's D8-LTD approach. All cells are identified in the FD raster that do not have inflowing cells but do have higher neighbors in their local 3×3 neighborhood. This is the set of ASCs. The highest neighbor of each ASC then has its FD altered to also point towards the downslope ASC. Because this cell would have already had an FD pointing towards a different downslope neighbor, this cell has now become dispersive. If there are more than one ASC in a cell's local neighborhood, it may have more than two outflowing neighbors, one for each ASC plus one for the original FD. Summit cells can shed flow to all eight neighbors.

FDs are stored using the same base-2 convention commonly used with MD8, allowing for pointers to multiple neighbors using a single value stored in each grid cell. For example, a cell flowing to its third and fourth neighbors (corresponding to the SE and S cells, if using the convention of ordering cells in a 3×3 starting from the NE and progressing clockwise) has an FD of $2^{3-1} + 2^{4-1} = 12$. A summit cell, flowing to all eight neighbors, would have an FD of $2^0 + 2^1 \dots + 2^7 = 255$.

Finally, the FD raster is used as the input for a flow-accumulation operation to create the final MDFA total contributing area (TCA), or specific contributing area (SCA) grid. For any cell $[r, c]$, the proportion of area (flow) directed towards neighboring cell, i , (F_i) is calculated as:

$$F_i = \begin{cases} p + (1 - p)/N_{out}, & i = FD_{PC} \\ (1 - p)/N_{out}, & i \neq FD_{PC} \end{cases} \quad [\text{Eq. 1}]$$

where N_{out} is the number of outflowing neighbors of cell $[r, c]$, FD_{PC} is the non-dispersive flow direction determined by the path-correcting algorithm, and p is the proportion of flow (0-1) that is given to FD_{PC} over and above any other secondary outflowing neighbors. This parameter preserves a preference toward the path-corrected direction in the flow accumulation grid. With $p=0.0$ (0%) there is no preference for any outflowing cell; with $p=1.0$ (100%) cells with multiple FDs will direct their flow entirely towards the original path-corrected direction and the algorithm behaves like a non-dispersive method. Therefore, MDFA has the flexibility of being either entirely non-dispersive ($p=1.0$) or partially dispersive ($p<1.0$). With $p<1.0$, it can be said that MDFA is minimally dispersive, since only the smallest possible subset of cells needed to eliminate ASCs will be dispersive.

III. CASE STUDY

The MDFA method was applied to a 19-million cell 1-m resolution lidar bare-earth DEM of Ponui Island, located approximately 35 km east of Auckland, New Zealand. The DEM was filtered using the Whitebox Feature Preserving Smoothing tool to remove surface roughness and noise in the original DEM while preserving significant breaks-in-slope. Smoothing is an important preprocessing method for DEMs used in flow-path modelling because micro-topographic scale roughness and noise produce abundant <1 m relief “summits” that are hydrologically insignificant at the relevant modelling scale. Topographic depressions were also removed from the smoothed DEM using Whitebox’s least-cost breaching method.

The resulting FD and SCA grids were compared with other common non-dispersive and dispersive flow algorithms in terms of their ASCs prevalence and their levels of dispersion (Table 1). Two measures of overall dispersion were used. The first measure was the percent of cells in the FD raster with multiple flow directions (%MFD), i.e., multiple outflowing neighbors. The second dispersion measure was related to the average percent of flow apportioned to secondary flow directions; a quantity referred to here as ϕ . The primary FD is the neighbor that receives the highest portion of flow, based on the flow algorithm’s apportioning method and all other directions are secondary.

Fig. 1 shows the SCA patterns generated using a selection of common flow algorithms and MDFA, with $p=0.75$ (Fig. 1C) and $p=0.0$ (Fig. 1D), for a small catchment draining into Motunau Bay, Ponui Island. This allows for qualitative visual comparisons of the resulting SCA patterns. Although tests MDFA with $p=0.5$ and $p=1.0$ are reported in Table 1, their SCA patterns are not presented in Fig. 1 for brevity.

TABLE I. ASC ABUNDANCE AND FLOW DIVERGENCE CHARACTERISTICS OF VARIOUS FLOW ALGORITHMS

Algorithm	ASCs (%)	%MFD	ϕ (%)
<i>Non-dispersive methods</i>			
D8	4.7	0.0	0.0
Rho8	18.1	0.0	0.0
MDFA ($p=1.0$)	13.1	12.5	0.0
<i>Dispersive methods</i>			
MDFA ($p=0.75$)	0.0	12.5	1.6
MDFA ($p=0.5$)	0.0	12.5	3.2
MDFA ($p=0.0$)	0.0	12.5	6.3
$D\infty$	0.8	95.3	24.4
MD8-Freeman	0.0	99.7	60.2

Figure 1. Comparison of SCA (m^2/m) patterns for a catchment draining into Motunau Bay, Ponui Island produced by D8 (A), Rho8 (B), MDFA with $p=0.75$ (C), MDFA with $p=0.0$ (D), $D\infty$ (E), and MD8-Freeman (F).

IV. DISCUSSION

As expected, MDFA FD rasters have no ASCs with $p < 1.0$. When the algorithm is treated as a non-dispersive method ($p = 1.0$), it was found to have an intermediate number of ASCs (13.1%) between D8 and Rho8 (Table 1). The reduced-dispersion algorithm D_∞ was the only dispersive method tested that produced ASCs, albeit a small number of these artifacts were present in the test data (0.8% of the total grid cells) compared with non-dispersive methods. Inspection showed that the D_∞ ASCs were largely associated with ridge positions, where D_∞ is known to misrepresent divergent flow [11].

MDFA (with $p < 1.0$) exhibited the least dispersion of any of the tested dispersive flow algorithms, by a significant margin (Table 1). Only 12.5% of the cells in the FD raster exhibited some level of dispersion, compared with >95% for D_∞ and nearly 100% with MD8-Freeman. Similarly, even the most dispersive form of MDFA ($p = 0.0$; no preference for the path-corrected FD at dispersive sites) demonstrated a 74% reduction in the average dispersion to secondary outflows ($\phi = 6.3\%$) than the second least dispersive algorithm, D_∞ ($\phi = 24.3\%$). This was expected, given that MDFA limits flow dispersion to sites in the upslope neighborhoods of ASCs, and with 87.5% of cells therefore treated non-dispersively. While adjusting the p parameter does not impact the total number of dispersive cells, raising the value from 0.0 to 0.5 did decrease ϕ from 6.3% to 3.2%, an 87% decrease in dispersion compared with D_∞ . Similarly, setting $p = 0.75$ lowered ϕ to 1.6%, a 93.5% decrease in dispersion compared with D_∞ . These findings indicate that p and ϕ are linearly and inversely related. The effects of varying p on the resulting SCA patterns were subtle (Fig. 1C and 1D) but discernable. It may be advisable for users to treat p as a mechanism for switching between dispersive ($p = 0.0$) and non-dispersive ($p = 1.0$) MDFA as required by the application, although more testing is required to find an optimal value.

The D8 SCA pattern showed extensive areas of unrealistically straight and parallel flow (Fig. 1A), that are not in the MDFA SCA rasters (Fig. 1C and 1D), even with $p = 0.0$. The application of a path-correction method resulted in more natural flow patterns in the MDFA rasters than D8. In fact, MDFA SCA patterns appear to follow broadly similar trends to the corresponding D_∞ and MD8-Freeman SCA patterns (Fig. 1E and 1F), although with visibly less overall dispersion. The level of dispersion in the SCA patterns increases from Fig. 1C (MDFA $p = 0.75$) to Fig. 1F (MD8-Freeman). This is apparent throughout the catchment but is particularly obvious along the main valley bottom (highest SCA values) where MDFA creates a mostly single-cell wide flow line compared with the thicker, more heavily dispersed flow lines associated with the two other dispersive algorithms.

Further testing is needed to compare the accuracy of the new method in predicting SCA patterns on mathematically defined surfaces, with known SCA values. This exercise may provide

better guidance on the setting of the p parameter. An implementation of the MDFA algorithm, developed using the Rust programming language, is available in the Whitebox Workflows (WbW-Pro) software.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a new flow algorithm, MDFA, which aims to produce more natural flow patterns than D8, no ASCs, like fully dispersive algorithms (MD8), and substantially less overall dispersion than current dispersion-limiting methods (D_∞). By limiting dispersion to cells where it is needed to ensure there are no ASCs, MDFA produces FD rasters where every grid cell is connected by a flow path to a downslope outlet cell and upslope to a summit, while most cells have a path-corrected (aspect aligned) single flow direction. MDFA occupies an optimal position in the fundamental flow-path modelling compromise between the needs for realistic flow patterns, no ASCs, and minimal use of dispersion.

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